

TGICA25_5-2c

UNECE Expert Forum on Climate Statistics

3-5 October 2017 in Rome

{source:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1dvBYKKgwYU0e2D3tTN2Yy3zSaYfWB0aqOaEtA3megE/edit> }

The forum will discuss a broad range of statistics related to climate (e.g. 4: Total support for fossil fuels/GDP; 27: Heat-related mortality;). There are a number of environmental ones (e.g. 23: Occurrence of extreme weather events), most of which have the comment "will be defined further" (see list here:

https://www.unece.org/fileadmin/DAM/stats/documents/ece/ces/2016/mtg/Session_3_Set_of_indicators.xlsx).

There are references to a further document for environmental statistics: "Framework for the Development of Environment Statistics (FDES 2013)"

<https://unstats.un.org/unsd/ENVIRONMENT/FDES/FDES-2015-supporting-tools/FDES.pdf> .

The FDES report contains the statement "The role of environment statistics is to process environmental and other data into meaningful statistics that describe the state of and trends in the environment and the main processes affecting them" --- this aim appears to overlap with much to the IPCC Assessment process.

In some cases, FDES states that methodological guidance for statistics will come from the IPCC (e.g. for temperature on page 51, for solar radiation, on page 52).